

Delivering the next generation of open Integrated Assessment MOdels for Net-zero, sustainable Development

D2.2 – MULTI-LAYERED STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT STRATEGY – UPDATE 1

WP2 – Codesign

26/04/2024

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EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

Much like the first version of the stakeholder engagement strategy (D2.1), this deliverable and its next version will serve as a reference document among consortium partners to describe the engagement strategy of the co-design phase of the project, including the methodology and approaches used for cross-disciplinary integration. The deliverable also documents the stakeholder engagement plan and its foreseen events, which is a dynamic plan for identifying and engaging all stakeholder groups.

It can also be used by policymakers and other stakeholder groups as a documentation of cross-disciplinary participatory processes and citizens' involvement.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

The DIAMOND multi-layered stakeholder engagement strategy will accompany and enrich the research process by enabling the exploration of the multiplicity of perspectives on how models can address concerns from the target groups, attending carefully to differences, complexities, and range of variation in the data.

It provides a description of the heuristic cross-disciplinary integration methodology adopted in the project; illustrates the co-design process involving researchers (e.g., modellers, SSH researchers), policymakers, business, social and environmental stakeholders, and citizens; and gives details on the stakeholder engagement plan.

In this update, we highlight how the integrated approach facilitates seamless interaction with other WPs, optimising co-creation and application of models, scenario building, and policy roadmap development. The strategy also takes stock of the work done in Phase 1 of the co-design process. It provides an update on the status of the stakeholder database, which—by the time of the submission of this document—incorporates more than 50 stakeholders pledging to actively participate in all DIAMOND stakeholder-related activities. Stakeholders from an initial mapping of 300 project partner contacts are continuously approached to gather their interest in participating in project activities like foresight workshops, meetings, and surveys, and ensure representativeness and diversity. These are expected to play a key role in the co-design process, and those initially allowing us to contact them will be invited to strategic foresight workshops alongside other experts, and other project activities.

The report also provides examples of the macro-questions to trigger each stage of the dialogue loop between researchers and practitioners aiming to co-create and assess climate change neutralisation actions, and the database structure for stakeholder engagement.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report. A future update will be delivered in month 29 of the project.

Preface

DIAMOND will update, upgrade, and fully open six Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) that are emblematic in scientific and policy processes, improving their sectoral and technological detail, spatiotemporal resolution, and geographic granularity. It will further enhance modelling capacity to assess the feasibility and desirability of Paris-compliant mitigation pathways, their interplay with adaptation, circular economy, and other SDGs, their distributional and equity effects, and their resilience to extremes, as well as robust risk management and investment strategies. This will be done via integration of tools and insights from psychology, finance research, behavioural and labour economics, operational research, and physical science. The project will develop a transdisciplinary scientific approach to legitimise the implementation process and co-create research questions that stretch the frontiers of climate science, as well as establish vibrant communities of practice to transparently open model enhancements and to develop capacities, thereby lowering the entrance barriers to the established IAM community.

ICCS	INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATIONS AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS	EL	
BC3	ASOCIACION BC3 BASQUE CENTRE FOR CLIMATE CHANGE - KLIMA ALDAKETA IKERGAI	ES	
CESAR	KRATENA KURT	AT	
CICERO	CICERO SENTER FOR KLIMAFORSKNING	NO	
CYI	THE CYPRUS INSTITUTE	CY	
E4SMA	ENERGY ENGINEERING ECONOMIC ENVIRONMENT SYSTEMS MODELING AND ANALYSIS SRL	IT	
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC IKE	EL	
COMILLAS	UNIVERSIDAD PONTIFICIA COMILLAS	ES	
ISINNOVA	ISTITUTO DI STUDI PER L'INTEGRAZIONE DEI SISTEMI (I.S.I.S) - SOCIETA' COOPERATIVA	IT	
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Executive Summary

This report constitutes an update of the multi-layered stakeholder engagement strategy of the DIAMOND project—as described in the preceding deliverable D2.1—for model co-development, scenario building and policy roadmaps’ co-creation exercises. This report takes stock of progress during ‘Phase 1 - Toward mutual understanding’, and provides details on activities and foreseen events belonging to Phase 1 and ‘Phase 2 – Towards knowledge co-production’, notably the strategic foresight workshops with stakeholders and the values and practice driven foresight with citizens.

Applying a heuristic cross-disciplinary integration methodology, the project aspires to both equip participating models with advanced decision rules and acceptance insights on different aspects of the transition, and improve the communication, usability, uptake, and relevance of modelling results to the wider society. The integrated assessment literature has long pinpointed the benefits and challenges of opening up participation of non-expert stakeholders in modelling activities and scenario development. Wide stakeholder participation and co-production can improve the legitimacy and robustness of the modelling outputs as well as help build consensus and a sense of ownership among stakeholders over specific solutions, reinforcing the success and speed of their implementation. In order to meet this challenge and achieve understanding between diverse actors with different scientific backgrounds and traditions of thought, it is necessary to create a common frame of reference.

DIAMOND will develop continuous dialogue loops between researchers and practitioners aiming to co-create and assess climate change neutralization actions - and two boundary objects – a Three Horizons participatory foresight framework and the suite of IAMs – which will support the DIAMOND cross-disciplinary dialogue loops. Each loop iteration starts by exploring together future scenarios – *A: EXPLORE SCENARIOS* –, then goes down to test possible solutions in the modelling simulation environment – *B: SIMULATE SOLUTIONS* – to go back to assess how these solutions actually fit into present reality – *C: VALIDATE OUTCOMES* – to end with the formulation of recommended further research and policy actions – *D: FORMULATE RESEARCH & POLICY AGENDAS*. To help shaping such specific dialogues, DIAMOND identifies a list of macro-questions to trigger each stage of the dialogue loop. Six specific dialogues with researchers and stakeholders will take place within the co-design process (i.e., circular economy and climate change mitigation; land use and nature-based solutions; household heterogeneity and distributional impacts; refining climate mitigation strategies assessment; integrating finance, labour dynamics and novel operationalization of well-being; and improving the electricity system assessment). One additional ethical foresight dialogue will be organised with a representative group of citizens, focusing on behavioural change and ethical issues of climate change neutralization.

In this report, the co-design process will be developed through a path identified by three, closely connected and sequential, phases: it starts with the definition of a common knowledge base and the common understanding of the content, goals, and limitations of the IAMs in the DIAMOND project, and continues with the co-development of tools and knowledge, and ends with the joint validation and quality assessment of modelling improvements. The concluded stages of Phase 1 of the co-design process have been conducted with a special focus on reaching mutual understanding within DIAMOND partners. The results of these activities have been integrated into the updated stakeholder strategy.

In order to meet the project expectations in terms of model co-development and policy scenarios and roadmaps co-creation, the stakeholder engagement in DIAMOND is structured through the involvement of three groups of stakeholders, namely the wider community of IAM developers and researchers, climate stakeholders and decision makers concerned with climate policymaking and/or climate change impacts, and citizens and civil society representatives). Ethical foresight is used to explain why the socio-political dimension needs to involve ordinary

citizens to lay down the foundations for mature information societies. The aim is to ensure a good balance of stakeholders across groups (and gender), and maintain stakeholder contacts throughout the project's life. The stakeholder database will be a vessel in all activities related to co-creation and engagement in WP2.

This report also provides updates on the interactions of the stakeholder engagement strategy with other work packages within the project framework, the approach to identify and include all relevant stakeholders in the co-design process of DIAMOND, the strategic foresight workshops with stakeholders and the values and practice driven foresight with citizens.

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1 Introduction

The main purpose of the DIAMOND project is to update, upgrade, and fully open six Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) that are emblematic in scientific and policy processes so that they provide a comprehensive and integrated framework of analysis to inform and support the design of climate policies based on:

- theories from a plurality of scientific disciplines that address causal factors and phenomena in the personal sphere (e.g. behavioural economics and psychology), in the socio-economic sphere (e.g. economics, social sciences), and in the ecological sphere (e.g., natural and life sciences)
- insights from societal actors themselves;
- empirical data from cross-national surveys of EU citizens to examine their mobility and energy use behaviours and willingness to change consumption behaviour.

Developing and implementing a comprehensive stakeholder engagement strategy is the primary objective of the stakeholder engagement activities conducted within WP2 of the DIAMOND project. This strategy aims to facilitate meaningful interactions and collaborations with stakeholders throughout the project lifecycle, particularly focusing on the integration and utilisation of updated IAMs within climate policy and decision-making processes.

Applying transdisciplinary methods, the project aspires to co-create the research questions, legitimise the implementation process and model development, and improve the communication, usability, uptake, and relevance of modelling results to the wider society.

To this end, the entire work structure of DIAMOND is operationalised with the help of a heuristic cross-disciplinary integration methodology for model co-development, application to scenario building and policy roadmaps' co-creation exercises. Recognizing that knowledge flows through various communities with diverse disciplinary perspectives and stakeholders, this mechanism ensures a balanced flow of information that is both relevant to policy needs and unbiased, providing comprehensive yet easily understandable information for all researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders involved.

In connection with the transdisciplinary approach that DIAMOND adopts, establishing meaningful linkages between science, policy, and society presents significant challenges. Specifically, engaging stakeholders in a meaningful way involves identifying the appropriate stakeholders and building trust. Delivering impactful outcomes for decision-makers is similarly challenging and is intertwined with technical model challenges. Political factors, such as competing agendas and a lack of transformative commitment from stakeholders, also influence the interplay between science outcomes and policy making processes.

To provide substance to these objectives and start their implementation, we illustrate:

- The heuristic cross-disciplinary integration methodology adopted in the project (Section 2);
- The co-design process involving researchers (modellers); policy makers; business, social and environmental stakeholders; and groups of citizens (Section 3);
- The detailed stakeholder engagement plan (Section 3).

In order to complement the theoretical framework of the multi-layered stakeholder engagement strategy described in the preceding deliverable D2.1 based on the progress made since its publication, here we provide updates on:

- The interactions of the stakeholder engagement strategy with other work packages within the project framework (Section 3.3.2);

- The facilitation of mapping stakeholders into our database (Section 4.1);
- The planning of upcoming stakeholder engagement events (Section 4.3).

This stakeholder engagement strategy is continuously updated and refined throughout the duration of the project, incorporating feedback, evolving based on stakeholder and project partner needs, and emerging new insights to ensure its effectiveness and relevance.

2 Cross-disciplinary integration methodology

2.1 Knowledge integration: the heuristic approach to cross-disciplinary integration in DIAMOND

The integrated assessment literature has long pinpointed the benefits and challenges of opening up participation of non-expert stakeholders in modelling activities and scenario development (Van Vuuren et al., 2012; Salter et al., 2010). Wide stakeholder participation and co-production can improve the legitimacy and robustness of the modelling outputs as well as help build consensus and a sense of ownership among stakeholders over specific solutions, reinforcing the success and speed of their implementation (McGookin et al., 2021). While engagement activities with decision-makers and societal actors have been used in the past as a reality check on IAM assumptions and for assessing feasibility of their outputs, they have been rarely used to feed or further develop IAMs with a plurality of perspectives on the low-carbon transition (Braunreiter et al., 2021). Apart from availability challenges, the sheer complexity of integrated assessments and the stakeholder heterogeneity in terms of expertise, beliefs, and values can often hinder meaningful engagement in modelling, scenario development, and impact (Elsawah et al., 2020).

To go beyond the current state-of-the-art, DIAMOND builds on the path opened by previous modelling exercises that recently started employing information from stakeholders.¹ That requires the constructive combination - or *integration* - of multiple forms of expertise and perspectives, or what we shall refer to as cross-disciplinary integration. We use 'cross-disciplinary' as a cover term for both interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary activity. When the context requires more specificity, the term 'interdisciplinary' is used to mean the integrative combination of disciplinary perspectives and 'transdisciplinary' to mean the integrative combination of disciplinary and stakeholder perspectives.² Going across the whole range of theoretical accounts,³ there is a large consensus that the integrative process consists in activities structured with the help of various techniques, yielding outcomes that advance cross-disciplinary research. These accounts also agree in taking integration to be *contextual*, i.e., dependent for its specific form on the context in which it is pursued, and *purposive*, i.e., a process intentionally implemented by researchers from several disciplines plus stakeholders working together in pursuit of objectives.

In the DIAMOND project, cross-disciplinarity is understood as a "heuristic integrative research approach" that adds cooperation between academic researchers and non-academic practitioners to the inner-scientific cooperation between various disciplines, facilitating the combination of inputs into an integrated output. This knowledge integration is more than just adding up disciplinary findings, but rather means the combination of heterogeneous knowledge assets with the aim of creating an identifiable synthesis product and new insights that go beyond the juxtaposition of different insights. To meet this challenge and achieve understanding between diverse actors with

¹ See for example:

- PARIS REINFORCE
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0048969721036214?via%3Dihub>
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/renewable-and-sustainable-energy-transition/special-issue/10ZRPC0C1P4>
- ENGAGE
[https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/frsus.2022.1063719/full?&utm_source=Email to authors &utm_medium=Email&utm_content=T1_11.5e1_author&utm_campaign=Email_publication&field=&journalName=Frontiers in Sustainability&id=1063719](https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/frsus.2022.1063719/full?&utm_source=Email%20to%20authors%20&utm_medium=Email&utm_content=T1_11.5e1_author&utm_campaign=Email_publication&field=&journalName=Frontiers%20in%20Sustainability&id=1063719)

² For discussion of these modes of research, see Klein (2010).

³ See for instance O'Rourke et al. (2015)

different scientific backgrounds and traditions of thought, it is necessary to have a common reference frame. In the DIAMOND project case, a common frame is provided by:

- the project objectives, with a specially emphasis objective 6 (O6);⁴
- using the whole range of available IAMs, WP3 upgrades and WP4 integration modules;
- using a Three Horizons participatory foresight framework to structure participants (researchers and stakeholders) climate change neutralization scenarios building activities;
- adopting a standard dialogue loop process for seven different but coordinated foresight exercises focused on:
 1. *Circular economy and climate change mitigation* (jointly with Task 4.1: An integrated framework for circular economy & mitigation).
 2. *Land use and nature-based solutions* (jointly with Task 4.2: Improving the representation of land use, nature-based solutions).
 3. *Household heterogeneity and distributional impacts* (jointly with Task 4.3: Distributional impacts: refining household heterogeneity).
 4. *Refining climate mitigation strategies assessment* (jointly with Task 4.4: Linking IAMs to climate/physical impact models).
 5. *Integrating finance, labour dynamics and novel operationalization of well-being* (jointly with Task 4.5: Integrating finance, labour dynamics, and well-being in IAMs).
 6. *Improving the electricity system assessment* (jointly with Task 4.7: A finer detail of electricity in IAMs for interconnectivity in EU).
 7. In addition, one ethical foresight dialogue will be organised with a representative group of citizens, focusing on *behavioural change and ethical issues of climate change neutralization*, also taking stock of Task 4.6: Representation of behavioural aspects & preferences for action results and of Task 4.3: analysis of household heterogeneity.

Figure 1 shows the DIAMOND dialogue loops between researchers and practitioners aiming to co-create and assess climate change neutralization actions, with the support of two “boundary objects”⁵: a Three Horizons participatory foresight framework and the suite of IAMs, WP3 upgrades and WP4 integration modules. As stated in the PARIS REINFORCE Policy Briefs⁶, models cannot be expected to produce fundamentally “true” policy insights,

⁴ To develop a transdisciplinary scientific approach to co-create the research questions, legitimize the implementation process and model development, and optimize the communication of project results, with representatives from policy, business, and civil society, allowing to translate the motives, concerns, and actions of decision-makers and citizens over climate action in measurable, quantifiable terms and to demonstrate how they can affect and contribute to the wider climate policy and sustainable development objectives.

⁵ Broadly speaking, in the field of cross-disciplinary research such diverse objects as scenarios (e.g., scenarios for the deployment of renewable energy), models (e.g., climate models), interdisciplinary frameworks and concepts (e.g., ecosystem services framework or biodiversity), spatial foci (e.g., case studies in a specific city or region), among others, are considered and applied as boundary objects. a boundary object works well if it establishes a shared language so that the different cooperating actors can represent their knowledge, enabling them to learn about their differences and dependencies (e.g., on undisclosed stereotypes) and facilitating a common process of knowledge transformation and integration.

⁶ PARIS REINFORCE Policy Briefs: <https://paris-reinforce.eu/publications/policy-briefs>.

but to feed **constructive dialogues** regarding inputs into the model, as well as the interpretation of results.

Figure 1. DIAMOND common cross-disciplinary goal

Source: Own elaboration

Now, the ambition of DIAMOND is to develop such structured dialogues to co-create and assess low carbon, net-zero or beyond net-zero target policies and actions. These dialogues, which begin in the project's co-design phase (WP2), will extend beyond the project's duration as an ongoing task within the DIAMOND open community (WP6).. This is represented in Figure 1 above by a loop connecting stakeholders/practitioners' real-life perspectives and the scientific evidence perspective embedded in the modelling structure and reality simulation functions, to co-produce a mutual understanding of the complex climate change challenge and devise possible responses. Each loop iteration starts by exploring together future scenarios – A: *EXPLORE SCENARIOS* –, then goes down to test possible solutions in the modelling simulation environment – B: *SIMULATE SOLUTIONS* – to go back to assess how these solutions actually fit into present reality – C: *VALIDATE OUTCOMES* – to end with the formulation of recommended further research and policy actions – D: *FORMULATE RESEARCH & POLICY AGENDAS*.

It is important to note that:

- After a first policy co-creation iteration that will be tested within the DIAMOND lifetime, the same heuristic approach of knowledge integration should be used to replicate integrated assessment exercises, continuing to involve both researchers and stakeholders, as a form of project exploitation activity.
- The whole DIAMOND project scope is too wide to develop a meaningful dialogue covering all the climate change neutralisation related issues simultaneously in one process. Therefore, it is suggested, after having identified and classified a wide range of stakeholders by their thematic expertise and interest, to engage them in an initial IAM user requirements-modellers capabilities matching workshop including specific thematic clusters sessions. This is expected to allow stakeholders and modellers to reach a common ground on what "should" and "can" be done and by which model, triggering potential adaptations to the model development strategy in WP3, and then produce stakeholder-driven research questions that will be addressed in WP4 and WP5 module and scenario development activities. This is expected to be

achieved by developing structured dialogues—using the same A-B-C-D loop logic—for specific extensions planned under ‘WP4 – Integrate & Expand’ and user-driven scenario exploration tasks in WP5 – Apply & Explore planned in the project.

In practice, modellers and stakeholders will work together in the first workshop to mutually understand which issues are useful and feasible to analyse with the available IAM capabilities and/or planned improvements, and co-design the specific dialogues settings (e.g., defining the modellers-stakeholders discussion groups) and research questions, to be addressed later on in the project and future exploitation activities. To help shape such specific dialogues, Table 1 lists “stem questions”⁷ that will be further specified depending on the specific dialogues’ contexts, to trigger each stage of the dialogue loop:

Table 1. “Stem questions” of the dialogue loop

<p>Stage A - EXPLORE SCENARIOS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Why we need to take climate change neutralization decisions now (challenging trends)? • What if scenarios (game changers, shocks)?
<p>Stage B – SIMULATE SOLUTIONS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What should be done to reduce global warming and adapt to climate change? (co-design of assumptions) • What model simulations can tell us? (interpretation of results)
<p>Stage C: VALIDATE SIMULATION OUTCOMES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do the suggested solutions fit back into present reality? If yes, how? If not, why not?
<p>Stage D. FORMULATE RESEARCH & POLICY AGENDAS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which further research and policy actions to do in practice?

Annex I shows a template to be filled for each of the seven planned structured dialogues with specific research questions based on the “stem” questions (Table 1) that will be co-generated by the modellers-stakeholders groups assigned to the seven dialogues in the first matching workshop; from the scientific perspective (by DIAMOND partners) in the first column, from the user perspective (invited stakeholders’ representatives) in the second column, and the shared questions consolidated by matching the two perspectives.

This template should be dynamically used to include relevant questions and outcomes of the discussions recursively at each stage of the structured dialogue process A, B, C and D.

2.2 Three Horizons foresight framework

Through the lens of a multi-layer stakeholder analysis, the DIAMOND project will engage invited representatives

⁷ In biology, stem cells are the body's raw materials — cells from which all other cells with specialized functions are generated. Here we use the notion of “stem questions” with the same meaning, i.e. general questions that will generate specialized questions in the different DIAMOND dialogue contexts (the seven thematic dialogues mentioned earlier).

of four main target layers of actors – policy makers, business and social stakeholders, environmental stakeholders, and citizens – together with researchers (DIAMOND modelling teams) in a cross-disciplinary process of user-driven climate change neutralization scenarios exploration, interpretation, and impact assessment. This activity will apply the Three Horizons participatory foresight framework. This is a tool that helps to structure the thinking about the future of a multi-disciplinary & multi-stakeholders' group in ways that spark innovation. It describes three patterns or ways of proceeding and how their relative prevalence and interactions evolve over time. The evolution from the established pattern of the first horizon to the emergence of fundamentally new patterns in the third occurs via the transition activity of the second horizon. The framework not only makes us think in interactive patterns, but more importantly it draws attention to the three horizons always existing in the present moment, and that we have evidence about the future in how people (including ourselves) are behaving now. As told by the main author, "the essence of Three Horizons practice is to develop both an individual and a shared awareness of all three horizons, seeing them as perspectives that must all come into the discussion, and to work flexibly with the contributions that each one makes to the continuing process of renewal on which we all depend. We step out of our individual mindset into a shared space of creative possibility." (Sharpe, 2013).

Horizon 1 is 'business as usual', or 'the world in crisis' (H1). It is characterized by 'sustaining innovation' that keeps 'business as usual' going. Horizon 3 is how we envision a 'viable world' (H3). We may not be able to define this future in large detail – as the future is always uncertain – yet we can intuit what fundamental transformations lie ahead and we can pay attention to social, ecological, economic, cultural, and technological experiments around us that may be pockets of this future in the present. Horizon 2 represents 'world in transition' (H2) – the entrepreneurial and culturally creative space of already technologically, economically, and culturally feasible innovations that can disrupt and transform H1 to varying degrees and can have either regenerative, neutral or degenerative socio-ecological effects.

At the point where the H2 innovations become more effective than the existing practices, they begin to replace aspects of 'business as usual'. Yet some forms of disruptive innovation ultimately get absorbed by H1 without leading to fundamental and transformative change, while other forms of disruptive innovation can be thought as a possible bridge from H1 to H3. It is useful therefore to classify H2 innovations into two categories. The first category is called H2- (Horizon 2 minus). H2- innovations change the technology employed and therefore disrupt 'business as usual' temporarily but without leading to a profound systemic transformation. The second category is H2+ (Horizon 2 plus). H2+ innovations offer a bridge to H3, leading to a structural change and transformation of the system itself. For example, providing power to the national grid via large-scale windfarms is on the H2+ as it is a strategy of moving towards a 100% renewable energy-based system, and on H2- innovation locked into an H1 mindset as it is still structurally supporting a centralized energy system. An example of a genuine H2+ innovation in this area could be a blend of diverse and decentralized renewable energy technologies that combine stand-alone and grid-connected options to increase the flexibility, efficiency, and resilience of the energy system overall.

The Three Horizons framework (Figure 2) will be used in the DIAMOND dialogue loops to discuss two typologies of scenarios: more conservative (H1) climate policy scenarios, mostly envisaging the deployment of the currently dominant technological trends and climate mitigation and adaptation policies; and more transformative (H3) scenarios, which consider not only the impact of new technological and economic measures, but also possible behavioural, social and cultural changes switching towards a regenerative economy paradigm. Both categories of scenarios will diverge from the reference scenario (named H0), which represents a "no-policy" action, where the business-as-usual trends are perpetuated, but with a different intensity and sustainability outcome (see box "*Switching to a regenerative economy*" below).

Beyond sustainability: We no longer have the luxury of just being less bad

H1 Conservative scenarios, where the system will stand in 2100 if current drivers and trends will continue unchanged

H3 Transformative scenarios, how the system will look in 2100 if new emerging paradigms will become dominant

H2 Window of opportunity, what can be done until 2050 to facilitate the best future outcome

Who is it for?
Stakeholders and public engagement to envision ‘the future we want’

Figure 2. 3H methodology applied to envision conservative vs transformative climate change neutralization scenarios (Participatory Foresight Framework)

Source: Adapted from J. Fullerton (2015), *Regenerative Capitalism*, Capital Institute, p. 43

Switching to a regenerative economy

The rationale of switching to a regenerative economy paradigm worldwide is increasingly evident. We are in a situation where rapid change to a healthy relationship with the planet is in order. In this respect, the concept of “regeneration” and “regenerative growth” moves our frame of discourse from “doing things to nature” to “participate as partners with and as nature”. At the core of the regeneration paradigm the economic system is conceived as a living system, working with the same universal pattern of self-organization, interdependence between and diversity of the various parts connected in a whole organic system. By taking this regenerative worldview we radically change the concept of sustainability. Rather than a “goal” measured by targets that can be achieved and then maintained forever after, sustainability is interpreted as a dynamic “process” of nature and human techno-sphere co-evolution, and a community-based process of continuous conversation and learning how to participate appropriately in the constantly transforming life-sustaining processes that we are part of and that our future depends upon. What a regenerative economy would sustain is the underlying pattern of planetary and human health, resilience and adaptability that maintain this planet in a condition where life satisfaction and human well-being can flourish.

The best-known example of regenerative economy is in the agriculture sector, where it is now technologically possible and economically competitive to produce food while simultaneously living the plot of land better off. But regeneration can work across all development sectors – not just agriculture – going beyond sustainability. The question in sustainable development was “*How can the economy work in such a way that we sustain or do not hurt the underlying (ecological and social) support systems?*” Now, the question in regenerative development becomes “*How can the economy work in such a way that we improve the capacity of the underlying support systems?*”. It is no longer enough to do no harm, sustainability and zero-waste and zero-emissions policies are noble goals, but we can and must do better than zero, we need to do good – this is the key message of regenerative economy.

Given the wide ‘diversity’ of scientific disciplines and stakeholders’ knowledge involved in the cross-disciplinary process, the DIAMOND dialogue loops will aim to match the scientific knowledge embodied in the IAM models with the values, mind-sets and perspectives of users/stakeholders. This “matching” is achieved by immersing the holders of different kinds of knowledge – scientific and experimental – in the dialogue setting represented in Figure 3 below as synergic sense making space. This conceptual representation of the DIAMOND dialogue setting considers:

- Three definitions of the term “sense” to identify a 3D field of synergic sense making from three angles: 1) sense as meaning (the scientific knowledge perspective), 2) sense as sensation/feeling (the practitioners knowledge perspective), and 3) sense as way to/direction (the forward-looking systemic perspective shared by both scientists and practitioners).
- Four fields of simultaneously co-existing systemic relations between agents – represented in the figure as superimposed layers, but tightly interwoven in reality: the ecological, economy & technology, society & culture, and political layers.
- A purpose-driven participatory process with structured dialogues spanning across the different layers, generated by using the Three Horizon scenarios framework.
- The synergic sense making game players, i.e., the participants involved in the dialogue loops from the different practical perspectives - policy makers, environmental stakeholders, business and social stakeholders, and citizens – and from nested holistic evidence-based perspectives. The latter are “holistic” insofar as they combine multiple disciplines to explain human behaviour (“ego-logy”), the economy and innovation dynamics

(“eco-nomy”), the ecosystem dynamics (“eco-logy”) and finally the influence of historical, societal, and cultural value contexts (“context-ology”, the focus of social science, art and humanities).⁸

Figure 3. The Diamond participatory foresight space

Source: Own elaboration

In this space – an immaterial boundary object - researchers (modellers) and different groups of stakeholders will meet and confront themselves from different perspectives. The scientific evidence-informed modelling of individual/household behaviour, economy, natural processes, and policy regulations will have to be married with the value-driven mindsets and experiential knowing of lay citizens, business and social stakeholders, environmental stakeholders, and policy makers, to discuss relevant topics in the different macro-layers: ecological, economy and technology, society and culture, and political.

In this process, conversations “across the boundaries” will help participants to disclose the ingrained disciplinary or mind frames, filtering their own vision of the reality of such things as, for instance, what is driving the adoption of a certain innovation. Modellers could discover hidden motivations and drivers, that could be feasible to include

⁸ It is useful to note that “ego-logy”, “eco-nomy” and “eco-ecology” are nested holistic perspectives, i.e. holons, while “context-ology” is key to contextualise any intervention – policy, decision, investment, etc. – in the real-life setting. A holon (Greek: ὅλον, from ὅλος, holos, 'whole' and -ov, -on, 'part') is something that is simultaneously a whole in and of itself, as well as a part of a larger whole. In other words, holons can be understood as the constituent part-wholes of a hierarchy. “Ego-logy”, looking to individuals, “Eco-nomy” looking to economic systems, and “Eco-logy” looking to ecological systems are in an holonic hierarchy. In other terms, holistic thinking considers the individual immersed in nested systems of relations internally with himself (body and mind organisms and functions), and externally in economic (market and non-market) and ecological relations. These systems of relations exist and evolves in concrete geographical, historical, anthropological, and cultural contexts - what human sciences study most (“context-ology”) - which eventually influence most of the policy makers decisions.

in a model to build more realistic representations, while stakeholders could overcome mental barriers against innovation by better understanding potential benefits or how to handle trade-offs. This whole process of collective intelligence' will be catalysed by sharing the third dimension shown in the cross-disciplinary space graphic, i.e., the imagination of future scenario pathways for climate change mitigation and/or adaptation.

2.3 DIAMOND integrated assessment modelling framework

The first boundary object is a purely abstract thinking – the Three Horizons scheme applied to frame transition scenarios. The second boundary object is still immaterial, but more concrete, being a collection of IAMs codified with software procedures and databases. While the first object has the highest interpretive flexibility – it is a shared language for collaborative future thinking that can be adapted to the purpose and context of specific foresight exercises to deliver scenario narratives and policy roadmaps – the second object it is unavoidably more rigid.

This dichotomy occurs because models are a code environment that provides a structured testing ground to simulate the effects of hypothetical assumptions, and they can be modified to a certain extent, but never without several limitations that modellers face (e.g., model limitations, data limitations, time limitations). Moreover, models are a broad approximation to reality: they are only as good as the assumptions that go into them, but there will be always relevant aspects that escape quantification and can only be considered in a qualitative fashion in the scenario narratives. Often these qualitative aspects are equally important as simulated outcomes, and they can be fundamental to interpret some quantitative results. This is also the reason why in DIAMOND we suggest combining the two boundary objects—the participatory foresight framework and the IAMs—together to feed forward-looking dialogue loops.

Table 2 summarises the list of models used in DIAMOND. For more information on the models, see project deliverable “D3.1 Model development strategy” and the I²AM PARIS platform.⁹

Table 2. Models used in DIAMOND

CLEWs
CLEWs is a nexus modelling framework for integrated assessment of resource systems and of interlinkages among energy, water, and agricultural systems as well as their impacts on—and vulnerability to—climate change.
GCAM
GCAM is a dynamic-recursive model with technology-rich representations of the economy, energy sector, land use and water linked to a climate model that can be used to explore climate change mitigation policies.
GEMINI-E3
GEMINI-E3 is a multi-country, multi-sector, recursive computable general equilibrium (CGE) model. It simulates all relevant markets, domestic and international.
NEMESIS
NEMESIS is a sectoral detailed macro-econometric model for the EU used to assess a wide spectrum of policies, including fiscal, budgetary, labour market, research and innovation, energy, climate, and environment.
OMNIA
TIAM is a leading partial-equilibrium, inter-temporal optimisation IAM, based on the TIMES model generator, along with which it has been used to support national and international climate policy. DIAMOND will produce

⁹ <https://www.i2am-paris.eu/>

OMNIA, featuring fully open access.

PROMETHEUS

PROMETHEUS is a global energy system model covering in detail the complex interactions between energy demand, supply and energy prices at the regional and global level.

3 The Co-design process

The co-design process elaborates on the stakeholder engagement, which, is structured through the involvement of researchers (modellers and experts), policy makers, business (i.e., industry and private sector), social and environmental organisations, and civil society representatives, to achieve model co-development and co-creation of policy scenarios and roadmaps.

3.1 The DIAMOND approach and objectives

DIAMOND conducts an open and cross-disciplinary research process based on adjusting and integrating knowledge from the wider IAM community and relevant experts from other scientific disciplines (e.g., psychology, behavioural economics, labour economics), as well as from policy, industry, and civil society stakeholders. This process accompanies and enriches all other methodological modules of the project: it will refine the requirements for model improvements (UPDATE & UPGRADE), pinpoint critical aspects for climate action that are currently missing from (or underrepresented in) IAMs (INTEGRATE & EXPAND), jointly co-create currently unexplored mitigation scenarios to simulate using the improved models (APPLY & EXPLORE), and codesign communication tools and applications of IAM results that are useful and user-friendly (OPEN). Most co-productive activities will take stock of experience/knowledge systematised in the *td-net toolbox*¹⁰ of transdisciplinary methods, allowing us to create a community of experts and societal actors that will inform project activities based on a distributed model of knowledge instead of a hierarchical one. This cross-disciplinary process will help us explore the multiplicity of perspectives on IAMs, understand how new models and scenarios address concerns from diverse stakeholders as well as map actionable knowledge and ensure usability via participatory development and validation.

Based on this general and conceptual framework, at the end of its implementation path, the DIAMOND co-design process will provide the following key outcomes:

- Co-produce the guiding questions to ensure transformational impact of our modelling framework in practice.
- Implement an interactive cross-disciplinary approach to inform modelling improvements and ensuing scenarios.
- Validate all project outputs to ensure policy relevance, usefulness in industry, and societal robustness.

3.2 Which types of stakeholders to be involved

As already outlined in the previous chapter, to implement in the most effective manner the DIAMOND cross-disciplinary co-design process, the project will involve three groups of stakeholders as shown in Figure 4 below:

¹⁰ The [td-net toolbox](#) is an online resource platform containing different methods for systematically co-producing knowledge in heterogenous groups across science and society.

Figure 4. Types of stakeholders in DIAMOND

Source: Own elaboration

In the first group, we will engage with the wider community of IAM developers and researchers to involve them in the development of the new, enhanced, open-source IAMs as well as relevant datasets and applications. Key experts to invite will include the coordinators of other European or national research IAM-oriented projects in support of climate, energy, and environmental/sustainability policies (e.g., WorldTrans¹¹, PRISMA¹², LOCOMOTION¹³, NAVIGATE¹⁴). To guarantee a robust interdisciplinary integration process, representatives from Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) disciplines will actively participate in the analysis of societal impacts related to climate policies.

In the second group, we will invite climate stakeholders and decision makers concerned with climate policymaking and/or climate change impacts to understand their perspectives, expectations, and requirements. This broad group encompasses several categories, including but not limited to European Commission and national policymakers (including negotiators in UNFCCC processes), local governments, industry, business associations, NGOs, unions, and other institutions.

In the third group, we will invite citizens and civil society representatives concerned with future impacts of climate

¹¹ <https://worldtrans-horizon.eu/>

¹² <https://www.netOprisma.eu/>

¹³ <https://www.locomotion-h2020.eu/>

¹⁴ <https://www.navigate-h2020.eu/>

change and climate-related actions on everyday life and the ethical acceptability of policy measures to further inform model development and increase societal relevance.

The actor constellation¹⁵ method will be used to identify the stakeholders that could contribute to and benefit from the project using, acknowledging the increasing complexity of global, multi-level environmental governance (Jänicke, 2008; Feldoff, Fanderl, Stockmann, Gahle, 2019).

3.3 The Co-design pathway

3.3.1 Multi-stakeholder co-design process

The co-design process will develop through a path identified by three, closely connected and sequential, phases: it starts with the definition of a common knowledge base and the common understanding about the contents, objectives and limits of the DIAMOND project IAMs, it then follows with co-developing tools and knowledge and ends by jointly validating and assessing the quality of modelling improvements.

Phase 1 – Towards mutual understanding and framing of project goals and requirements.

In the first stage of the project, and notably Task 2.2, the focus is placed on exploring how IAMs are being perceived by different stakeholders and identify relevant understandings on current IAM gaps and needs. The “but why” technique (Virapongse et al., 2020) is used to extensively discuss the existing situation and reach to the root causes of problems with current IAMs as well as define research questions from the perspective of different fields of knowledge (project partners) and practice (stakeholders). Moreover, multi-stakeholder discussion groups (Fry, 2021) are employed to ensure that our project asks relevant research questions from the point of view of societal priorities and stakeholder interests and will complement this qualitative approach with representative studies to examine how IAM outputs are understood and interpreted by the public. Based on this multimethodological assessment, we will identify the respective demand for knowledge that the improved IAMs will need to provide. In this context, we will also identify citizen-sensitive research topics—i.e., related to behavioural change and societal transformation practices at small scale, but with the potential to deliver effective impacts if upscaled (Nikas et al., 2020). The main aim of this initial phase is reaching a mutual understanding of models’ interpretations and needs. The output will take the form of research questions from the perspectives of both researchers and stakeholders and of shared co-created research questions that will be used in the next Phase 2 of knowledge co-production to trigger the DIAMOND dialogue loops illustrated in Section 2.2.

During this first period of the project (between deliverable D2.1 and this updated version), under T2.2, the first two stages of phase 1 have been concluded, with a focus on reaching mutual understanding within DIAMOND partners. Stage 1 focused on familiarising with DIAMOND’s ‘problem space’ and outlined project member perceptions around the DIAMOND mission and opportunities; gaps and limitations of IAMs; and stakeholder engagement barriers and opportunities. Stage 2 focused on reaching mutual understanding within the consortium and explored how project members envision different codesign activities, and clarified DIAMOND partner understandings and expectations of stakeholder engagement. The findings of these activities have been integrated into the updated stakeholder strategy (see deliverable “D2.4 - Stakeholder-informed research questions”, more details).

¹⁵ According to the Swiss Academy of Sciences (SCNAT), an actor constellation is a role-play, in which all scientific and societal actors involved in a project are represented and positioned around the central research question. The distance from an actor to the research question, and to other actors, expresses how relevant (s)he is in the project.

Through these two initial stages of mutual understanding, a set of codesign activities have been produced under three criteria: i) strengthening the external and internal community of practice will allow DIAMOND to learn from other experiences and transfer knowledge on such co-productive processes in IAMs; ii) achieving more effective stakeholder engagement will focus on developing a richer understanding of stakeholders, when to engage them, how to improve communication with them, and how to achieve a heterogenous representation of stakeholders; and iii) an elaboration on where to focus co-design and co-productive activities in model development. With these three criteria well framed, a rich set of information has been created to be used in Stage 3. Stage 3 will focus on reaching mutual understanding between stakeholders and DIAMOND partners and commenced in January 2024.

The codesign activities will be designed as multi-stakeholder discussion groups, a flexible, tailor-made format that caters to the different needs depending on the codesign activity. ETH will run these multi-stakeholder discussion groups in parallel with the foresight workshops described in Phase 2 and the results of the two formats aim to feed into one another.

More details on the description of this phase are provided in deliverable “D2.4 - Stakeholder-informed research questions”.

Phase 2 – Towards knowledge co-production

This is the main phase of the stakeholder engagement process, aiming to involve the different groups of stakeholders either in co-developing the IAMs upgrades and in co-producing scenarios making use of the expanded tools. Along with members from the broader IAM community (in collaboration with H2020 ECEMF¹⁶ and the IAMC¹⁷, openmod¹⁸, OpTIMUS¹⁹, CCG²⁰, IEA-ETSAP²¹, IEW²², EMP-E²³, and CLEWs²⁴ communities/networks), we will organise capacity building activities to co-develop new modelling capabilities and harmonise modelling assumptions/inputs in order to address across-the-board gaps and needs of the community. The use of these improvements will not be restricted to the DIAMOND modelling armoury but will be made available to duplicate in/export to other IAMs and accompanied with adequate support and training material. In parallel, we will engage with the group of stakeholders and decision makers in scenario planning workshops to envision and assess alternative, feasible, and desirable policy scenarios. We will reflect on validity problems associated with existing reference/baseline scenarios to which modelling research anchors and subsequently improve these scenarios by accounting for current policies, restrictions, and game-changing issues. Thus, we will first understand what “we are currently looking at” before grasping “what we need to do against that”. For this, we will employ a “strategic foresight” methodology (Iden et al., 2017), a systematic approach for stakeholders to look beyond current expectations, account for a variety of plausible future developments, and identify implications for policies. More in detail, we will apply here the heuristic approach to cross-disciplinary integration described in Section 2.2 to frame six dialogue loops focused on the DIAMOND WP4 planned extensions. In addition, an “ethical foresight” approach (Floridi and Strait, 2020) will be used to engage with our citizens group, looking into the ethical implications of technology development and policies, focusing on what is actually feasible in everyday

¹⁶ <https://www.ecemf.eu/>

¹⁷ <https://www.iamconsortium.org/>

¹⁸ <https://openmod-initiative.org/>

¹⁹ <http://www.optimus.community/>

²⁰ <https://climatecompatiblegrowth.com/>

²¹ <https://www.iea-etsap.org/>

²² <https://www.internationalenergyworkshop.org/>

²³ <http://www.energymodellingplatform.org/>

²⁴ <https://www.sparkblue.org/dashboard/CLEWs>

practice, and privileging—within this—what is environmentally sustainable, socially acceptable, and preferable by the citizens (see section 3.3.3.1 below). This will be complemented by representative surveys allowing to make assumptions about the support of various policies and scenarios in the public as well as associated risk perceptions. Through this approach, we will define reference scenarios and modelling improvements for IAMs that respond to the most relevant citizens’ concerns, perceptions, needs, and desires. As described in section 3.3.3.2 below, climate-friendly practice workshops with citizens will be organised to develop scenarios for a sustainable transition based on local practices and behavioural shifts that could be transformed into powerful, bottom-up actions for climate mitigation and adaptation, drawing from recent experience of consortium partners in H2020 projects (e.g., Nikas et al., 2021).

Finally, the outputs of the strategic and ethical foresight exercises will be synthesised in Task 2.3.3 using a Situation Analysis (Task 2.3.3). This qualitative interpretative method will explore the multiplicity of perspectives as they will emerge in the dialogue loops structured with the heuristic cross-disciplinary integration approach described in Section 2.2.

Phase 3 – Towards model co-ownership

In the last phase, all stakeholder groups will be brought together to jointly validate and assess the quality of the modelling improvements and resulting scenarios with respect to scientific robustness and contribution to the IAM community (researchers), practical relevance (decision makers, industries, and NGOs), and societal robustness (civil society). We will use the emancipatory boundary critique (Pohl, 2020) to uncover priorities and assumptions of the different stakeholders within project outputs—for instance, system boundaries that were set when creating the new IAMs and aspects that were stressed or neglected in defining scenarios. Most importantly, we will employ the “most significant change” method (Wülser, 2020) to evaluate the impact of implemented model improvements and scenarios and discuss them considering stakeholders’ interests. Finally, we will identify potential impacts that the project can achieve in the mid- and longer term.

Figure 5. The co-design pathway in DIAMOND

Source: Own elaboration

3.3.2 Interactions of the stakeholder engagement strategy with other project work packages

The DIAMOND project aims to collaboratively formulate research questions, validate the implementation process and model development, and enhance the communication, usability, adoption, and societal relevance of modelling outcomes. In pursuit of these objectives, the entire framework of the DIAMOND project is operationalised using a heuristic cross-disciplinary integration methodology for co-developing models and scenarios, applying them to

scenario design, and engaging in policy roadmap creation exercises. Recognising that knowledge flows across communities with diverse disciplinary and stakeholder perspectives, this approach ensures a policy-oriented (demand-driven) yet objective (rigorous and scientifically credible) dissemination of comprehensive (analytical and detailed) yet understandable information to all researchers and policymakers/stakeholders involved.

Additionally, this integrated approach facilitates seamless interaction with other work packages within the project. By leveraging cross-disciplinary insights and collaborative efforts, the project aims to optimise the co-creation and application of models, scenario building, and policy roadmap development across different phases and components. This interactive engagement fosters synergies, enhances the relevance and impact of project outcomes, and promotes effective knowledge dissemination within and beyond the DIAMOND project framework.

A robust stakeholder engagement strategy is essential for ensuring the success and impact of the project's objectives across various work packages. A key aspect of this strategy is the interaction of the stakeholder engagement strategy with other work packages within the project framework. There exists interconnections and synergies between stakeholder engagement activities and various project components. Stakeholder inputs and feedback should contribute to the advancement and refinement of project objectives across different WPs, as illustrated in the following sub-sections.

3.3.2.1 WP3 – Update & Upgrade

One of the main objectives of DIAMOND is to update and expand existing IAMs, incorporating stakeholder information and the potential interconnection with bottom-up sectoral models, in order to overcome existing limitations and make sure that the outcomes produced will be robust, trustful, and socially relevant. While these models have largely contributed to global and regional policymaking and climate change mitigation strategies (Weyant, 2017), scientific literature has pointed out some weaknesses or areas of improvement that should be considered for the robustness of future IAM applications. For example, IAMs have frequently been considered as black boxes, with opaque input assumptions that do not allow a full understanding of the uncertainties embedded in the produced outputs (Pfeninger et al., 2018). Other critiques note the limited representation of socioeconomic and political barriers that different policymakers face for the implementation of alternative policies (Peng et al., 2021).

Model development in WP3 will ensure open-access, transparency, and the ability to address the most relevant research questions from different stakeholders and policymakers at different scales. The main features of each model, e.g., regional, sectoral and technological coverage, as well as scenario/policy-specific information such as implementable policies and mitigation measures have been collected through an internal survey. This information is crucial to collect and incorporate stakeholder inputs on how model development can meet their needs, which will be an important input for the final model development plans.

In order to incorporate stakeholder insights into each model in an effective and efficient way, the modelling teams will need to identify the research questions that stakeholders want to address and use stakeholder information to identify the most crucial aspects to be improved (i.e., geographical and temporal scales, sectoral coverage, input information and assumptions, misrepresented dynamics and uncertainties, and interconnection with additional sectoral models). As an initial step, modellers will establish "clear asks" directed towards the relevant stakeholders. Following this, WP2 will closely collaborate with WP3 to engage pertinent stakeholders in contributing technical insights to inform the modelling process. More details on the model development strategies can be found on deliverable D3.1.

3.3.2.2 WP4 – Integrate & Expand

In WP4, DIAMOND expands IAM capabilities by integrating models, theories, and insights from a diversity of disciplines, including behavioural economics, psychology, finance research, labour economics, and climate science. A key output from this will be a series of fully-fledged integrated assessment frameworks with capabilities that transcend the scope and capacity of individual IAMs operating separately.

Comprehensive cross-sectoral insights and methodologies from social sciences are reflected in DIAMOND to assess lifestyle changes and desirability, alternative growth and welfare, labour diversity/shifts. Considering the WP4 planned extensions, researchers from diverse communities are guided to build common understandings of their shared questions, early integrating findings from the following fields of practice considered in the project:

- Circular economy and climate change mitigation;
- Land use and nature-based solutions;
- Household heterogeneity and distributional impacts;
- Refining climate mitigation strategies assessment;
- Integrating finance, labour dynamics and novel operationalization of well-being;
- Improving the electricity system assessment;
- Behavioural change and ethical issues of climate change neutralization.

Effective collection of research questions requires careful consideration of the project's scope, objectives, and desired outcomes. It involves input from diverse stakeholders, including subject matter experts, collaborators, and end-users, to ensure that the questions reflect the broader context and address relevant issues. By systematically gathering and refining research questions, DIAMOND will establish a strong framework to pursue the integration and expansion of IAMs.

3.3.2.3 WP5 – Apply & Explore

The engagement of different stakeholders for scenario development and policy analysis has become essential for the trustfulness and social acceptance of IAM results (Miller & Wyborn, 2020). While IAM modellers use stakeholder inputs to better represent certain model parameters or dynamics, stakeholders have only recently started to be part in the scenario design (Nikas et al., 2023). The co-creation and co-production of alternative scenarios, taking onboard collective stakeholder insights, is an active research line for the IAM community to produce results that are more meaningful and socially relevant. In addition, stakeholder information is key to identify model weaknesses and potential improvements.

Either formulating new or improving existing scenarios requires planning to ensure adequate stakeholder engagement. Work package 5 (WP5) focusing on scenario development began their tasks in collaboration with WP2 during January 2024, and multi-stakeholder discussion groups are organised as part of Task 2.2 (Phase I; see above) that feed into and run in parallel with the foresight workshops. Stakeholders are going to be engaged early on for 'Task 5.1 - Unpacking scenario pipeline uncertainties', with other Tasks progressively starting to scope of the new scenario definition space and prioritisation in 2024. The model developments (WP3) and extensions (WP4) link to the applications in WP5 (Tasks 5.2-5.5) and there will be various steps of harmonisation to ensure consistency across stakeholder engagements in the different WPs. Engaging stakeholders early on will aid identifying synergies with other tasks in WP3 and WP4, which will act as one of the criteria for prioritising development and expansion the models.

3.3.3 Citizens' involvement

3.3.3.1 Why do we need to involve citizens?

In the process of building a mature information and sustainable society, the real challenge is not only building technological innovation but also governance of social and ethical impacts. Ethical foresight is crucial to explain why the socio-political dimension needs to involve ordinary citizens to lay down the foundations for our mature information and sustainable societies.

When policymakers, both in political and in business contexts, wonder why we should engage in moral evaluation when legal compliance is already available, the answer should be clear: compliance is necessary but insufficient to steer society in the right direction. Ethical problems matter and we must engage with stakeholders dealing with such ethical problems. Regulation indicates what the legal and illegal moves in the game are, but it says nothing about what the good and best moves could be to have a better society (EDPS Ethics Advisory Group, 2018). So, the task of ethical foresight is not simply to forecast the most plausible future developments, but also to determine which ones should grow and which ones should not. In other words, we need to anticipate and steer the ethical development of technological innovation. We can do this by looking at what is actually feasible, privileging firstly what is environmentally sustainable, secondly what is socially acceptable and finally, ideally, choose what is socially preferable (Floridi, 2018).

3.3.3.2 Climate-friendly practice workshops

Public engagement plays a vital role in fostering understanding, collaboration, and informed decision-making within communities, ultimately shaping policies and initiatives that reflect diverse perspectives and address shared concerns (Pidgeon, 2021). Citizens and civil society representatives concerned with future impacts of climate change and climate-related actions on everyday life and the ethical acceptability of policy measures will be involved within DIAMOND through climate-friendly practice workshops, taking inspiration from the transition practice workshops held in the ENABLE.EU Horizon 2020 project²⁵. The DIAMOND Climate-friendly Practice Workshop will aim to elicit the opinions of 40 citizens to further inform model development and increase societal relevance. The results of the workshop will also feed the exploitation plan with possible replication opportunities of the DIAMOND approach into other projects.

Ethical foresight workshops with citizens will aim to elicit a better understanding of peoples' values, beliefs and habits that drive everyday consumption practices, including transportation use and households' investment in durable goods and service, and to reflect on how these contribute at an aggregated level to global warming and climate change, with the help of IAM-based analyses.

Within the DIAMOND project, climate-friendly practice workshops will be designed to foster ethical foresight and public validation, synergising with the behavioural approach of WP4. These workshops will elicit the opinions of citizens to further inform model development and increase societal relevance. They are also expected to feed the exploitation plan with possible replication opportunities of the DIAMOND approach into other projects.

Climate-friendly practice workshops will aim to engage a diverse and heterogeneous group of participants, as those identified through an empirical survey—currently conducted in Task 4.6—to investigate behavioural changes for climate-neutral action, which gathers cross-national data on EU citizens' mobility, energy use

²⁵ <http://www.enable-eu.com/>

behaviours, and willingness to adopt sustainable consumption practices. Participants will reflect a broad spectrum of backgrounds and perspectives, guided by the insights gleaned from the T4.6 survey, especially on electric vehicle adaption and house insulation. The workshop agenda will be adjusted accordingly to ensure that the participation focus aligns with the survey findings, catering to the diverse interests and needs of attendees. Citizens will be invited to: i) define socially acceptable and preferable practices to simulate in the IAMs; ii) evaluate whether reference scenarios fit with their perceptions, needs and desires; and iii) envision actionable practices and behavioural shifts towards more sustainable scenarios.

The workshops will facilitate qualitative debates centred around concrete choices and their impacts on sustainability, engaging participants in meaningful discussions to explore actionable practices and behavioural shifts that contribute to more sustainable scenarios. Through this dialogue, attendees may provide valuable insights and perspectives, enriching the qualitative understanding of climate-friendly practices.

A key component of the workshops involves framing people-relevant research questions that resonate with citizens' everyday experiences and concerns: energy at home, mobility, food, and waste. These questions should guide discussions on socially acceptable and preferable practices to simulate in IAMs, ensuring that modelling efforts are grounded in real-world perceptions and aspirations.

DIAMOND partners have expressed a need to increase engagement with a diverse range of civil societies and NGOs. These actors can guide research questions and include aspects that may not have accounted for before in scenario development. Partners feel it is important to include citizens from all spheres. The private sector is an important and largely missing stakeholder group who can inform modellers on technology developments as well as feasibility of policy adoption. Government and institutions are also important due to their major influence in decision-making, but here partners pointed out that different levels of government should be engaged, even local.

The next Section presents details on the stakeholder engagement plan, including timelines for the abovementioned described activities.

4 Stakeholder engagement plan

4.1 Organisation of stakeholders mapping and database

The DIAMOND project emphasises heterogeneous and inclusive stakeholder engagement as a critical aspect of its approach to addressing climate change mitigation. It recognises the importance of ensuring a balanced representation of actors who are influenced by or influence climate change dynamics. This approach aims to foster collaboration and consensus-building among diverse stakeholders to enhance the relevance and impact of the project's outcomes.

To achieve this goal, DIAMOND has implemented a comprehensive and continuously updated strategy for identifying, engaging, and maintaining the involvement of relevant stakeholders throughout the co-design process. This strategy involves several key components:

- **Stakeholder identification and inclusion:** The project takes a rigorous approach to identifying and including all relevant stakeholders in the co-design process. This process is designed to be inclusive and transparent, ensuring that stakeholders from various sectors, disciplines, and geographic regions are represented.
- **Continuous engagement:** The project is committed to keeping stakeholders engaged over the duration of the project. This includes regular communication, updates, and opportunities for collaboration and feedback to ensure ongoing participation and commitment.
- **Examining stakeholder types and contributions:** The project examines the different types of stakeholders involved and their expected contributions to the project. This analysis considers the specific interests, expertise, and capabilities that stakeholders bring to the table, ensuring that their involvement is meaningful and productive.

A critical aspect of the stakeholder engagement strategy involves mapping stakeholders across different layers, tailored to the specific needs of different project tasks. This tailored approach ensures that stakeholders are appropriately engaged based on their relevance to specific aspects of the project. Understanding which stakeholders would be most useful involves a nuanced assessment of their expertise, perspectives, and potential contributions.

To implement the DIAMOND cross-disciplinary co-design process in the most effective manner, the project involves three groups of stakeholders, as described in the preceding deliverable D2.1:

- a) the wider community of IAM developers and researchers, to involve them in the development of the new, enhanced, open-source IAMs as well as relevant datasets and applications.
- b) climate stakeholders and decision makers concerned with climate policymaking and/or climate change impacts, to understand their perspectives, expectations, and requirements.
- c) citizens and civil society representatives concerned with future impacts of climate change and climate-related actions on everyday life and the ethical acceptability of policy measures, to further inform model development and use in order to increase societal relevance.

ISINNOVA organises the process of managing the database of stakeholders to be involved in DIAMOND. The database contains the following fields:

- Name
- Surname

- Email
- Partner Reference
- Organization
- Individuals' position within organization
- Main Field of activity/interest: *Agriculture, Citizen Association, Climate, Construction, Economy, Energy, Engineering, Food, Health, Labour, Model development, Natural Environment, Policy government, Social sciences and humanities (SSH), Technology, Transport/mobility.*
- Country
- City
- Category: *Academia, Cities Network, Consultant, EU policymaker, International Agency, Local Energy Agency, Local Government, National Agency, National Government, NGO, Private sector/Industry, Regional Government, Research Center, Trade Union.*
- Level of Activity: *Global, National, Regional, Local.*
- Date of registration

During the first stage of the database development, more than 300 relevant stakeholder contacts from all project partners were gathered, with the aim to ensure a good balance of stakeholders across groups (and gender).

In order to have heterogenous stakeholders involved in DIAMOND, partners reviewed the breakdown of the stakeholder database and noted key stakeholder groups/backgrounds missing and how to fill those gaps. By doing this, partners were involved in ensuring that the database is heterogenous through their active participation in searching for and adding stakeholders of interest. Ensuring a heterogenous representation of stakeholders is very important to the success of effectively co-producing model developments that represent society more accurately. It is crucial, during initial engagements with stakeholders, to effectively communicate DIAMOND's expectations and in turn receive feedback and perceptions of those expectations from stakeholder, as well as incorporate stakeholder perceptions and expectations into the codesign focus.

4.2 The introductory survey: register in the DIAMOND stakeholder pool

Based on this initial stakeholder mapping, stakeholders have been contacted in the past months via a survey to express their interest in joining the project activities, on the merits of their previous contact with each project partner. As core members of the co-design process, they have been told that they may be invited to participate in a series of events and/or activities, including but not limited to foresight workshops, bilateral meetings/interviews, discussion groups with other stakeholders, and surveys, always in consideration of their valuable time. For example, in the first phase of this process, they will be invited to participate with other experts in three strategic foresight workshops described in the next section.

The survey asks for permission to contact the stakeholders again in the context of this project and allow us to understand their interest in and level of knowledge of IAMs. A total of 73 experts completed the survey, 53 of whom expressed interest in participating in DIAMOND collaborative activities such as workshops. The rest agreed to participate in project-related online surveys rolled out by the consortium and/or to be kept informed of the project activities and results (e.g., by around 6 newsletters per year). Following GDPR guidelines, only stakeholders that provided their permission to be contacted again will be kept as part of the DIAMOND stakeholder database. In the survey, we made sure to include all necessary disclaimers for stakeholders to be able to exercise their rights

based on GDPR guidelines. Stakeholder that did not respond will not be part of the database. It therefore falls to the partners’ jurisdiction whether they can be invited through personal communications (depending on their previous contacts and familiarity—always in respect of GDPR rules).

The summary of the survey results is shown in Figures 6-8 below.

Figure 6. Professional capacity of the stakeholders that agreed to participate in collaborative activities

Figure 7. Familiarity of stakeholders agreeing to participate in collaborative activities with IAMs

Figure 8. Familiarity of stakeholders agreeing to participate in collaborative activities with the project IAMs

The respondents' fields of expertise cover a wide range of disciplines²⁶, such as sustainability, energy, climate change, economics, and policy. Table 3 provides a categorised summary of the areas of expertise based on the provided open-ended response.

Table 3. Disciplines and Areas of Expertise of the stakeholders

Discipline	Areas of Expertise	Num. Stakeholders
Energy and Climate Modelling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long-term energy planning • Energy decarbonization scenarios • Renewable energy power system integration • Energy system modelling (Vensim, CGE, TIMES) • Carbon pricing policy and market modelling • Energy scenario interface and user interaction • Energy system analysis and modelling • Capacity development in energy systems 	21
Economics and Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecological economics • Macroeconomics • Climate economics • Economic modelling and integration with energy systems • Climate change policy and mitigation scenarios 	16

²⁶ Some stakeholders may possess expertise spanning multiple disciplines. Therefore, their contributions and perspectives may reflect diverse knowledge areas within the project's scope.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>International macroeconomics and finance</i> • <i>Legal regulation in renewable energy</i> 	
Sustainability and Sustainable Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Sustainability sciences</i> • <i>Social and ecological sustainability</i> • <i>Integrated assessment of urban resource systems</i> • <i>Sustainable development policy and analysis</i> 	6
Systems Analysis and Modelling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Integrated land use modelling (bottom-up IAMs)</i> • <i>Macroeconomic implications of climate policies</i> • <i>Energy system capacity expansion modelling</i> • <i>Life cycle assessment (LCA) and sustainability analysis</i> • <i>Linear programming for energy systems</i> • <i>Social lifecycle assessment</i> 	7
Technology and Engineering	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Energy system engineering and planning</i> • <i>Energy access and open-source software engineering</i> • <i>Mobility and urban transportation planning</i> • <i>Engineering for energy transition</i> • <i>Assessment of energy and transport technologies</i> 	9
Stakeholder Engagement and Participation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Participative research methods and stakeholder engagement</i> • <i>Barriers and enablers of collective forms of energy-citizenship</i> • <i>Stakeholder engagement in energy communities</i> 	4
Other Expertise Areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Risk modelling and reliability analysis</i> • <i>Project management and strategy development</i> • <i>Applied ethics, research ethics, and epistemology</i> • <i>Conservation, agriculture, agroforestry and biotechnology</i> • <i>Comparative politics and international cooperation</i> 	9

These diverse areas of expertise reflect a comprehensive approach to addressing complex challenges related to climate change, energy transition, sustainability, and policy formulation. The respondents' collective knowledge and skills encompass various dimensions of sustainable development, offering valuable insights and contributions to the DIAMOND project's objectives and activities. The stakeholder database will be a vessel in all activities related to cocreation and engagement in WP2.

4.3 Planning of the stakeholders engagements events

4.3.1 Phase 1 – Towards mutual understanding and framing of project goals and requirements

Progress on this Phase was reported in Section 3 of this deliverable, while outstanding activities and a detailed description of this phase is provided in deliverable “D2.4 – Stakeholder-informed research questions”.

4.3.2 Phase 2 – Towards knowledge co-production

This phase aims to involve the different groups of stakeholders either in co-developing the IAM upgrades and in co-producing alternative, feasible, and desirable policy scenarios that respond to the most relevant stakeholders’ and citizens’ concerns.

4.3.2.1 Strategic foresight workshops with stakeholders (Task 2.3.1)

A core element of stakeholder engagement within the DIAMOND project is organising participatory foresight workshops informed by cross-disciplinary integration methodologies and leveraging the Three Horizons foresight framework, introduced in section 2.2, to drive collaborative policy scenario building and long-term impact assessment exercises.

Key research questions will be developed to guide model co-development, scenario building, and the co-creation of policy roadmaps, emphasising a participatory approach that incorporates insights from societal actors. This collaborative process ensures that scenario-building efforts are inclusive, relevant, and aligned with stakeholder needs and expectations.

One of the key objectives of the strategic foresight workshops is to integrate IAM developers into the discussion process. This integration allows for the exploration of broad and overarching questions related to climate action. The workshops enable modellers to interact with stakeholders from various sectors and disciplines, translating technical insights into accessible and actionable strategies. By engaging with modellers, stakeholders can contribute their expertise and perspectives to shape the development of scenarios and policy roadmaps. This integration ensures that modelling efforts align with real-world needs and priorities, promoting the relevance and applicability of project outcomes.

Three main workshops are going to be held, all organised via online conference platforms with interactive tools, such as inter alia a MURAL²⁷ board, supporting the interaction and lasting approximately 3 hours.

- **Requirements Workshop:** co-define the requirements of IAM improvements to best respond to relevant stakeholders’ concerns.
- **Reference Scenarios Workshop:** validate realistic reference scenarios describing where we are heading based on current policies.
- **Alternative Scenarios Workshop:** envision and assess alternative/desirable policy scenarios.

For each event, ISINNOVA will:

- Ensure a transparent and inclusive participation process and timely invitation.

²⁷ <https://www.mural.co/>

- Prepare and send background documents to the participants before each workshop. A brief will be shared containing information regarding the project, aims and progress as well as the agenda and the objectives of the related workshop.
- Apply the facilitation techniques most suitable for the workshop aims and participants.
- Draft workshop reports to be then analysed to gather insights for the next stages.

The workflow will be articulated in three consecutive steps as follows: preparatory step phase, on-stage step (online delivery) and reporting step:

1. **Preparatory step:**

- Workshop organisation: selecting dates, streamlining the invitation process, and defining workshops roles. Efforts will be made to send an invitation to workshop participants a month before the workshop.
- Workshop operational design: selection of facilitation techniques and supporting tools, preparation of agenda, workshop guide and report template. A draft will be shared with the project partners no later than two weeks before the workshop.
- Workshop brief: prioritising comprehensible items to be presented to the workshop participants thus allowing swift and effective interaction during the workshop sessions. A brief will be sent to the workshop participants no later than one week before the workshop.

Following, the mutual understanding principles set forth in Phase 1, continuous interactions between project partners will take place to ensure that the workshops' scope and structure will be useful for the activities of DIAMOND.

2. **On-stage step:** The three specialised workshops will follow a similar structure in which:

- In the first session, the team shortly recaps the workshop objectives and methods.
- In the second session, interactive breakout rooms will be moderated by a member of the team to gather inputs from the participants. Though it is challenging to ensure that each and every participant has a chance to express their views, this constraint can be satisfactorily addressed by making use of boards and polls, which will allow participants to contribute. Nonetheless, efforts will be made to ensure that all voices are heard within the workshops.
- In the third session, a plenary discussion will be held to compare and summarise the group's discussion findings (qualitative and/or quantitative).

For each workshop, the following roles will be distributed among the DIAMOND team members:

- Moderator and rapporteur:
 - Remind participants of the task and encourage the initiation of the discussion;
 - Try to keep the discussion on topic by bringing it back if it starts to drift. Prompts will be provided for each activity;
 - Ensure all participants have a chance to contribute to the discussion: encourage non-contributing participants to engage;
 - Double-check that breakout room operate as intended;
 - Capture the key points of the discussion;
 - Synthesise all different perspectives;
 - Share the highlights of the discussion during the plenary session in roughly 5 minutes;
- Discussant:
 - Have the technical role of co-host to share slides;
 - Present the project and the relevant model(s) to the discussion in roughly 15 minutes;

- Try to be as receptive as possible to participants ideas and sensitivities;
 - Intervene in the discussion when explicitly requested by participants and/or moderator;
 - Note taker:
 - Have the technical role of co-host to facilitate the operation of breakout rooms;
 - Capture the discussion by taking as much notes as possible (depending on the rules of the workshop; e.g., whether the Chatham House Rule applies or not).
3. **Reporting step:** To summarise workshops results and feed them to the next stages of the project in order to influence model development and drive applications that are customised to the needs and abilities of each stakeholder group.

Table 4. Current structure and timeline for the organisation of strategic foresight workshops

WHAT	HOW			WHEN	WHO
	Mode	Methodology	Frame		
Requirements	Online	3H	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Breakout rooms ● MURAL support 	June 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Team facilitators ● Stakeholders
Reference Scenarios	Online	3H	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Breakout rooms ● MURAL support 	Month 24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Team facilitators ● Stakeholders
Alternative Scenarios	Online	3H	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Breakout rooms ● MURAL support 	Month 25	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Team facilitators ● Stakeholders

4.3.2.2 Requirements Workshop (June 2024)

The first strategic foresight workshop in the DIAMOND project is the Requirements Workshop, which serves as a foundational step in aligning stakeholder needs and expectations with modelling objectives. The Requirements Workshop aims to kickstart collaborative efforts between modellers and stakeholders. Its primary objective is to confront and reconcile the expectations of both parties, ensuring a shared understanding of useful and feasible stakeholders-driven research and IAMs application. In this workshop, we will co-define the requirements of IAM improvements to best respond to relevant stakeholders’ concerns. This workshop is particularly relevant for WP3 and WP4.

The workshop aims to engage stakeholders who are part of the research modelling community and utilize IAMs in specific sectors. By involving these stakeholders, who have expertise in model development and sector-specific applications, the workshop fosters interdisciplinary collaboration and knowledge exchange. This engagement ensures that IAMs are not only technically robust but also relevant and applicable to real-world challenges faced by different sectors.

The expected outcome of the Requirements Workshop is a clear set of stakeholders-driven priorities that will be used by IAM researchers to guide model refinement and scenario design, ensuring that research efforts are aligned with stakeholder interests and priorities.

4.3.2.3 Reference Scenarios Workshop (Month 24)

The Reference Scenarios Workshop is the project's second strategic foresight workshop, dedicated to scenario development and stakeholder engagement. This workshop focuses on validating realistic reference scenarios that depict the trajectory based on current policies and practices. The primary objective of the Reference Scenarios Workshop is to validate and refine reference scenarios that describe the projected future trajectory under existing

policies and trends.

During the workshop, participants will analyse and discuss research questions related to scenario development, particularly those identified within WP5. These questions will serve as guiding principles for scenario design and will help identify key areas of focus for further investigation and analysis. Research questions and task queries from WP5 will be shared with stakeholders to gather feedback and insights, allowing for the adjustment and enhancement of scenario parameters based on diverse perspectives and expertise.

Concrete scenario developed during the workshop will be tailored to the input and involvement of stakeholders. By incorporating stakeholder feedback and insights, the scenarios are envisioned to become more robust, relevant, and representative of real-world dynamics.

It is worth noting that DIAMOND partners think that stakeholders often misunderstand that IAMs do projections (scenarios) rather than predictions (forecasts), and the importance of understanding this difference between the two communities has been internally highlighted.

4.3.2.4 Alternative Scenarios Workshop (Month 25)

The Alternative Scenarios Workshop is the last step of the DIAMOND project's strategic foresight approach, aiming to envision and assess alternative and desirable policy scenarios. This workshop serves as a platform for stakeholders and modellers to explore innovative and transformative pathways that deviate from current trajectories. By envisioning alternative scenarios, participants can assess the potential impacts of different policy interventions, technologies, and societal changes on climate action. Through collaborative discussions and scenario-building exercises, the workshop will foster creativity and critical thinking, enabling stakeholders to co-create plausible and aspirational futures that align with sustainable development goals. By engaging in this process, stakeholders contribute valuable insights and perspectives that inform the development of holistic and forward-thinking policy recommendations and strategies. Ultimately, the Alternative Scenarios Workshop will empower stakeholders to explore novel approaches and envision pathways towards a more resilient and sustainable future.

4.3.2.5 Values and practice driven foresight with citizens (Task 2.3.2)

Details on how to organise the climate-friendly practice workshop engaging citizens, introduced in section 3.3.3.2, will be described in the next update of the stakeholder engagement strategy (D2.3), also based on the results of Tasks 4.3 and 4.6, which will respectively clarify to what extent and how the heterogeneity of households' behaviour and behavioural change for desirability of climate action is represented in IAMs, which are expected to produce a set of answers these models can provide to questions on the matter.

However, a general approach that we plan to follow to engage the citizens can already be described. This will be done considering the following principles:

- **Concrete choices and impacts:** citizens, divided in focus groups, will be asked to consider their concrete habits, behaviours and choices in the real everyday life practice concerning:
 - Energy at home, especially house insulation;
 - Mobility and transportation;
 - Food consumption;
 - Waste;
- **People-relevant research questions:** a first question will aim to raise awareness of the global consequences of their own individual behaviours and choices, that emerge when data are aggregated in model computations

and scenarios. Other questions will follow that apply a subsidiarity principle, asking what can be done first by people/households themselves, what can be done by people aggregated in communities of collective consumption or production, and then what should be done by governments, at different levels (local, regional, national, global). The following are examples of such questions:

- To what extent and how people choices have an impact on climate change?
 - What can we do by changing our individual/household behaviour and/or investment choices to mitigate/adapt to climate change?
 - What can be done at the community level, by changing collective behaviour?
 - What the governments can/should do to help people change behaviours towards climate-neutral everyday life and investment in durable goods/services choices?
 - To what extent and how this will contribute to change people well-being?
- **Citizens' engagement strategy:** an efficient approach will be to find synergies with the online citizens survey organised in Task 4.6 for selecting and recruiting the target of 40 citizens to investigate behavioural changes for climate-neutral action. Survey responses could be scanned to identify groups of citizens with different personal profile (age, gender, other relevant characteristics asked in the survey) and typology of responses that may show different values and habits, and this information could be used to form and recruit focus groups of balanced participants to co-create and discuss relevant research questions in the four fields of everyday life practice: energy at home, mobility, food, and waste. Online citizens workshops can be organised with plenary sessions involving the whole group of citizens and DIAMOND modellers, followed by breakout session for the four fields (approximately 10 citizens for each session), and again a plenary session to wrap up conclusions and recommendations.

4.3.3 Phase 3 – Towards model co-ownership

This phase will commence on Month 31. The detailed description of this phase will be provided in the final update of this deliverable and deliverable "D2.5 Stakeholder-informed research questions – Update".

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ANNEX I. “Stem-questions”

PHASE	“STEM-QUESTIONS”		CURIOSITY-DRIVEN RESEARCH QUESTIONS (science perspective)	USER-DRIVEN RESEARCH QUESTIONS (stakeholder perspective)	CONSOLIDATED RESEARCH QUESTIONS (shared focus)
Phase 1 Mutual understanding	STAGE A: EXPLORE SCENARIOS	Why we need to take climate change neutralization decisions now?			
		What if scenarios?			
Phase 2 Knowledge co-production	STAGE B: SIMULATE SOLUTIONS	What should be done to reduce global warming and adapt to climate change?			
		What model simulations can tell us?			
	STAGE C: VALIDATE OUTCOMES	Do the suggested solutions fit back into present reality? If yes, how, If not, why not?			
Phase 3 Model co-ownership	STAGE D: FORMULATE RESEARCH & POLICY AGENDAS	Which further research and policy actions to do in practice?			